

Abstract

Acupuncture for Managing Breast Cancer - Efficacy and Mechanisms.

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Abstract

Breast cancer is a major global cause of cancer-related deaths, profoundly affecting patients physically and psychologically. Traditional treatments often come with undesirable side effects, which underscores the importance of exploring complementary therapies. Acupuncture, a practice rooted in traditional Chinese medicine, is drawing interest for its possible advantages across a range of health issues. This review evaluates the current top-level evidence regarding the use of acupuncture in managing breast cancer. Acupuncture showed potential in alleviating stress, depression, and insomnia in individuals with breast cancer. It also proved effective in addressing side effects from treatment, such as pain, fatigue, and menopausal symptoms. However, the evidence for some outcomes is still limited. The ways in which acupuncture works are intricate and warrant further research. Acupuncture appears to be a promising complementary therapy for breast cancer patients, potentially improving both their physical and psychological well-being. While current research is encouraging, more high-quality studies are necessary to establish clear treatment guidelines.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Breast cancer.

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